

Performance Appraisal and Employee Job Engagement in Mobile Telecommunications Companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

JAMES, Kelechi Faith

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Administration and Management,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni.

kelechi.james@iaue.edu.ng

Phone Number: 08034813783

Dr. S. P. Asawo

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Administration and Management,
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt.

sove.asawo@ust.edu.ng

Phone Number: 08037244139

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between performance appraisal and employee job engagement in the four leading telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. Measures of employee engagement include dedication, vigor and absorption. The study adopted goal setting theory which helps to explain the basic concept. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. The simple random sampling and quasi-experimental design was used in a non-contrive setting. The Taro Yamane's formula was employed to arrive at the sample size of 147. The reliability of the instrument was achieved using Cronbach Alpha coefficient. Data generated were analyzed and presented using both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman's Rank Order Correlation aided with Statistical Package for Social Sciences, version 24.0. The findings revealed a positive and significant relationship between performance appraisal and employee job engagement. The study concludes that when employees perceive the appraisal process as transparent, developmental and aligned with actual performance standards, they are more likely to exhibit higher levels of dedication, vigor and absorption. It further recommends that mobile telecommunications companies should adopt clear, transparent and standardized performance appraisal, in order for workers to be dedicated. In addition, the companies should implement continuous performance conversations, as such feedbacks support and sustains vigor and absorption, which make employees to remain connected to organizational objectives.

Keywords: *Absorption, Dedication, Employee Job Engagement, Performance Appraisal, Telecommunications Companies, Vigor.*

INTRODUCTION

The industry stream is basically centered on the outcomes of a psychological state: performance, retention, and commitment. The industry stream had readily adopted the concept of workplace engagement even though little evidence existed to support it. According to Remo (2012), Khan (1990) was the first to introduce the concept of employee engagement

at work to the academic realm. He suggested that people can use varying degrees of their selves, physically, emotionally and cognitively in the work roles they perform. In broad view, the conceptual vagueness and measurement issues can be attributed to this “bottom-up” manner in which the engagement construct evolved. Since the industrial approach to studying engagement in the workplace has been driven by the bottom line, organizational profitability, many human resource consultants and practitioners nowadays offer advice on how engagement can be promoted and leveraged (Macey & Schneider, 2008). Employee engagement is a relatively new concept that is being studied and utilized by two sectors: the academic sector and the industry sector. There is a clear delineation between the academic and the industry view of engagement (Wefald & Downey, 2009).

Performance appraisal is the name given to the formalized review of the way in which an individual is performing on his/her job in an organization. According to Tamunomiebi and Zeb-Obipi (2013), appraisal is usually done periodically, bi-annually or annually. They also explained that it determines organization’s success. Performance appraisal is the formal assessment of staff in order to determine his performance level. It is an accepted personnel function that some mechanisms have to be adopted to assess workers from time to time in order to ascertain how well they are doing their job (Obi, Onyekwelu, Obinna and Mohammed, 2016).

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Organizations in the mobile telecommunications sector are faced with low employee job engagement as a result of lack of vigor, dedication and absorption and this has led to loss of significant amount of revenue due to low productivity, poor customer service and high level of employee turnover in the sector. Past research has indicated the link between low

employee engagement and high employee turnover. The study of Gallup incorporation argued that merely 13% of employees are engaged in their job, this implies that the remaining percentage are not engaged, therefore, this study seeks to fill the lacuna or gap through performance appraisal.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between performance appraisal and employee engagement.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1.1 Conceptual Framework of Performance Appraisal and Employee Job Engagement.

Source: Author’s Desk Research (2024)

Objectives

From this purpose, we can derive the following objectives.

- i. To examine the relationship between performance appraisal and dedication in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.
- ii. To examine the relationship between performance appraisal and vigor in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

- iii. To examine the relationship between performance appraisal and absorption in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study;

- 1 What is the relationship between performance appraisal and dedication in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- 2 What is the relationship between performance appraisal and vigor in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria?
- 3 What is the relationship between performance appraisal and absorption in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the research questions above, the following hypotheses were drawn;

H01: There is no significance relationship between performance appraisal and dedication in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

H02: There is no significance relationship between performance appraisal and vigor in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

H03: There is no significance relationship between performance appraisal and absorption in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Concept of Performance Appraisal

It is a tool used by the organization to review and evaluate the performance of employees over a certain period of time. Murphy (2004) stated that in many organizations, performance appraisals are expected to fulfill numerous functions including feedback, coaching, goal setting, skills development, pay determination, legal documentation, employee comparison and layoff selections. Aforo and Antwi, (2012) postulated that performance appraisal system is comprised of setting goals, communicating feedback, participation and incentives for employee's performance. Fletcher (2004) disclosed that performance appraisal remains the primary way of discussing and acting on the development of the individual. Chubb, Reilly and Brown (2011) insisted that performance appraisal is designed to stimulate employee performance as well as organizational performance. Performance evaluation is a systematic process of measuring a person's performance in the job, based on predetermined performance criteria (Clake, 2011) and it aligns itself to the organization strategies and provides a lively link to general and specific human resource functions (Vukotich, 2014).

Performance appraisal is one of the core functions of human resource development (Hughes, 2019: 79). Dessler, (2013: 274) opined that performance appraisal "means evaluating an employee's current and or past performance relative to his or her performance standards". Performance appraisal has three broad purposes: strategic, administrative, and developmental (Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart, & Wright, 2016). Some authors like Brown and Redman, (2017), Dessler, (2013), Mamoria and Rao, (2014) and Torrington, Hall, Taylor, & Atkinson (2017) have stated that there are several methods and techniques for measuring the performance of employees in organizations which can be traditional or modern techniques. Traditional techniques include the straight ranking method, paired comparison method, graphic rating scales, forced description method, the checklist method, essay method, critical incidents, group appraisal and field review while Management by objectives (MBO), assessment

centers, 360-degree appraisal, human asset accounting, balanced scorecard and behaviorally anchored rating scales (BARS) are considered as modern techniques of the appraisal system.

Concept of Employee Job Engagement

An engaged employee tends to take initiative, the organization's needs, strength and supports the organization's culture and values, stay focused and alerted, and he or she can make a difference (Macey, 2006). According to Men (2015), engagement is characterized by energy, absorption, involvement, efficacy, vigor, dedication, enthusiasm and a positive state which are described as catalysts for employee performance. According to Gallup (2002), engaged employees work with full passion and drive innovation and bring the organization a step forward. Engagement is defined by scholars as high level of commitment and involvement an employee has towards the organization (Saks, 2006), emotional and intellectual commitment to the organization (Truss, Soane, Edwards, Wisdom, Croll & Burnett, 2006), positive attitude held by the employee towards the organization and its values (Robinson, Perryman & Hayday 2004) and harnessing of organization members' selves to their work roles, expressed physically, cognitively and emotionally (Khan, 1990) as cited in Asawo, Gladys and Gabriel (2017).

Dedication

Dedication as a measure of employee job engagement refers to being strongly involved in one's work, and experiencing a sense of importance, passion and challenge. It refers to a strong involvement which results in positive feelings like inspiration, significance, pride and enthusiasm (Gubman, 2004). Having a dedicated employee is considered an asset to the organization. Dedication involves desire, commitments ownership and a continual strive to improve (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2003). Rayton and Yalabik, (2014), opined that dedication is about being inspired, enthusiastic and highly involved in your job. It is an individual deriving

a sense of significance from work, feeling enthusiastic and proud about the given job, feeling inspired and challenged by the job according to Song, Kolb, Lee and Kim (2012). Mauno, Kinnunen and Ruokolainen (2007) stated that employee dedication has conceptual similarities with job involvement. MacLeod and Clarke, (2009) concurred that employee dedication can be described as a strong psychological involvement or the sense of identification, which the worker feels for his or her work. However, there is a distinction between dedication and job involvement.

Vigor

Vigor is often about vitality. Many descriptions of vitality point to the Latin word *vita*, meaning “life,” as in life force, life energy, liveliness, lust for life. According to Bakker and Demerouti (2008), vigor can be described in terms of an employee’s levels of energy and the mental resilience while doing his or her work. Vigor is an affective construct (Shriom, 2004). Moreover, vigor is perceived as the opposite of emotional exhaustion (Schaufeli et al., 2003) amongst the dimension labeled energy (Gonzalez-Roma, Schaufeli, Bakker & Lloret, 2006). Nevertheless, as Sonnentag and Niessen, (2008) already stated that individuals may experience different levels of energy at the end of the day. Sometimes an individual can leave their workplace at the end of the day and still be full of energy.

Absorption

Asawo, et al., (2017) defined absorption as characterized by being totally and happily immersed in one’s work and having difficulty detaching oneself from it. In other words, it involves high concentration, assimilation and embeddedness at work to the extent that one finds it difficult to separate from work. With regards to dedication, it is about being inspired, enthusiastic, and highly involved in one’s job (Rayton & Yalabik, 2014). Employees are engaged to have an energetic and effective relationship with their work activities, and they see

themselves able to deal well with the demands of their work (Schaufeli, Shimazu, Hakanen, Salanova & De Witte, 2017). May, Gilson and Harter (2004) concurred that absorption means that an individual is deeply focused and determined engrossed in working, while the time moves rapidly.

Theoretical Foundation

The underlying theory that best explains the subject of the study is the goal setting theory propounded by Edwin Locke. According to Locke & Latham (2006) goals refer to future valued outcomes, the setting of goals is first and foremost a discrepancy-creating process.

Goal setting refers to goal being set for the future for subsequent performance of an individual or organizations. When individuals or organizations set more difficult goals, they perform better on the other hand, if the set goals are easy then the performance of the individuals or organizations decreases (Locke & Latham 2006). Therefore, when goals are set in an organization, it motivates the employees to improve on their level of job engagement in order to achieve the stated goals. This theory by Locke was developed inductively after studying the psychology of organizations and industries over the years. When a person or organization is committed to achieving goals and do not suffer from any conflicting goals, then the achievement of the goal is positive. Hence, in order to apply goal setting in a day-to-day work, a ‘commitment analysis’ should be undertaken to draw up objectives and goals. It allows continuous improvement in objectives and performance standards (Moynihan, 2008). In addition, goal setting helps in developing an action plan designed to guide people and organizations, thereby making it a major component of personal development and management.

Donovan and Williams (2003), stated that the advantages of goal setting theory include choice, efforts, persistence, cognition and limitation. Furthermore, many researchers pointed

out that there is a positive correlation between goal setting and improved business and organizational results. This is because goal setting theory encompasses all aspects of building organizations with efficiency (Koppes, 2014). According to Locke and Latham (2006), there are five basic principles that allow goal setting to perform better. These include clarity, challenge, commitment, feedback, and task complexity.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Relationship between Performance Appraisal and Employee Job Engagement

Performance appraisal gives a chance to both the employee and the supervisor to review the goals and targets that they set together and also to confirm whether the employee is on course, how far they are from accomplishing their goals and also to identify any possible challenges that the employee may face. Bridger (2014) insisted on the need of the open performance appraisal process to eliminate bias ratings. Ajibola, Mukulu and Simiyu (2019) in their study on Performance appraisal and employee engagement, does tenure matter? Evidence from South-West Nigeria, adopted a descriptive research approach. Respondents were sampled from employees of one State University, wire industries, and oil and gas sector in Osun State capital, Nigeria. Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used to select 250 respondents. The questionnaire was used for data collection. Only 139 (54.51%) questionnaires were found useful for the analysis. Descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analyses were used for the data analysis. The findings of the study reveal that performance appraisal had positive significant influence on employee engagement but the relationship between performance appraisal feedback and employee engagement was found to be statistically insignificant.

METHODOLOGY

Baridam (2001) defined research design as a framework or plan that is used as a guide in collecting and analyzing the data for a study. Research design deals with determining how to conduct the research and the methods used (Williams, cited in Ahiauzu and Asawo (2016). This study adopted a cross-sectional survey strategy and the quasi-experimental research design was used in a non-contrive setting. The population of the study include employees from the 4 leading telecommunication companies in Nigeria as obtained from NCC 2024 Annual Report that render voice and data services in Rivers State, Nigeria. They include: Mtn, Globacom, Airtel and 9mobile. They have a total of two hundred and thirty- two (232) workers as obtained from their various Human Resource Departments. The Taro Yamane's formula was employed to arrive at the sample size of 147. The reliability of the instrument was achieved using Cronbach Alpha coefficient. Data generated were analyzed and presented using both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman's Rank Order Correlation aided with Statistical Package for Social Sciences, (SPSS) version 24.0.

Data Analysis and Results

Table 1. Correlations Matrix for Performance Appraisal and Measures of Employee Job Engagement

			Performance Appraisal	Dedication	Vigor	Absorption
Spearman's rho	Performance Appraisal	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.732**	.559**	.624**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.000
		N	124	124	124	124
Dedication	Dedication	Correlation Coefficient	.732**	1.000	.487**	.710**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000
		N	124	124	124	124
Vigor	Vigor	Correlation Coefficient	.559**	.487**	1.000	.428**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000
		N	124	124	124	124
Absorption	Absorption	Correlation Coefficient	.624**	.710**	.428**	1.000

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.
	N	124	124	124	124

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, version 24.0

Ho₁: There is no significance relationship between performance appraisal and dedication in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

The result of correlation matrix obtained between performance appraisal and dedication was shown in Table 1. The correlation coefficient of 0.732 confirms the direction and strength of this relationship. The coefficient represents a strong positive correlation between the variables. The tests of significance shows that that this relationship is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.01$. Therefore, based on observed findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between performance appraisal and dedication in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significance relationship between performance appraisal and vigor in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

The result of correlation matrix obtained between performance appraisal and vigor was shown in Table 1. The correlation coefficient of 0.559 confirms the direction and strength of this relationship. The coefficient represents a moderate positive correlation between the variables. The tests of significance shows that that this relationship is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.01$. Therefore, based on observed findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between performance appraisal and vigor in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Ho₃: There is no significance relationship between performance appraisal and absorption in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

The result of correlation matrix obtained between performance appraisal and absorption was shown in Table 1. The correlation coefficient of 0.624 confirms the direction and strength of this relationship. The coefficient represents a strong positive correlation between the variables. The tests of significance shows that that this relationship is significant at $p < 0.000 < 0.01$. Therefore, based on observed findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between performance appraisal and absorption in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Having tested the three hypotheses postulated in the study, the researcher discovered that there is a significant positive relationship between performance appraisal and employee job engagement in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. The finding of this study corroborates with a study conducted by Govender and Bussin (2020) in their study on performance management and employee engagement, a South African perspective. The findings reveal that relationship exist between performance management and employee engagement and that an increase in employee engagement would result in improved performance of employees and subsequently the organization. The researcher also discovered that performance appraisal as a dimension of performance management is significantly related with dedication, vigor and absorption which are measures of employee job engagement which is in line with the work of Ajibola et al., (2019) who in their study on performance appraisal and employee engagement, does tenure matter? Evidence from South-West Nigeria. The findings of the study reveal that performance appraisal had positive significant influence on employee job engagement.

CONCLUSION

In consonance with the findings of this study, a well-designed and fairly administered appraisal system plays a critical role in strengthening employees' psychological connection to their work. Evidence from this study indicates that when employees perceive the appraisal process as transparent, developmental and aligned with actual performance standards, they are more likely to exhibit higher levels of dedication, vigor and absorption. In addition, performance appraisal is not merely an administrative exercise, but a strategic tool that shapes motivation and engagement. Appraisals that emphasize continuous feedback, goal clarity and recognition foster a supportive work climate where employees feel valued and empowered and such environment will enhance both individual performance and organizational productivity. The study concludes that performance appraisal significantly and positively relates with employee job engagement in mobile telecommunications companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The study recommend that mobile telecommunications companies should adopt clear, transparent and standardized performance appraisal in order to increase the dedication of workers.
2. Mobile telecommunications companies should allow employees participate in goal-setting and self-assessment because it makes them have a sense of ownership which enhances their vigor.
3. Finally, the companies should implement continuous performance conversations, as such feedbacks support and sustains absorption, and make employees to remain connected to organizational objectives.

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